

**ASSESSING THE EXTENT ON THE USE OF RESEARCHER-MADE SURVEY-
QUESTIONNAIRE****John M. Caparros**

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ABSTRACT

Researcher-made survey-questionnaire is commonly used as research instruments in the administration of quantitative researches. This research instrument is widely used across various fields including education and social sciences. This study assessed the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire emphasizing its benefits, challenges and implications for research quality. The study used quantitative method specifically descriptive research and participated by 300 randomly selected public school teachers in elementary and junior high schools in the Philippines. Findings of the study revealed that teachers assessed researcher-made survey-questionnaire as highly practical and easy to utilize because of its customization and relevance aspects. In addition, the study further concluded that teachers experienced several benefits in the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire as it is highly-engaging, contained tailored indicators, cost-effective and flexible. On the other hand, teachers frequently struggled in the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaires as they experienced that reliability testing and validation process were complex. Conversely, they were not challenged in terms of time-consuming aspect and potential bias when they developed a survey-questionnaire. Thus, the study proposed a training program as an output of the study which may help teachers in the academe to develop and further expand their technical knowledge in the preparation and utilization of researcher-made survey-questionnaire in education studies.

Keywords:

extent, researcher-made, survey-questionnaire, instrument, practical, customization, relevance, validity, reliability

INTRODUCTION

Research becomes quantifiable when relevant and highly scientific research instruments are used. Researchers in this manner are deeply focused on the technicality and procedural aspect in the development of research instrument. Notably, research instruments are fundamental to meet the established research objectives and answer the formulated research questions in a certain research work. In long lines of published and unpublished researches the use of research instruments depend on the research design which researchers use in their study. One of the critical aspects of research development and formulation is the construction and formulation of researcher-made survey-questionnaire. Under this type of research instrument, this is commonly used in quantitative research designs. The construction of researcher-made survey-questionnaire has long been put into scientific scrutiny emphasizing its relevance and extent of modification and customization. In this regard, some researchers use researcher-made survey-questionnaire considering its convenience, practicality and time-efficiency in the formulation and construction of such instrument. On the other hand, some scholars believed that the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire can only invite several aspects of scientific scrutiny and

evaluation whereas researchers may tend to be questioned as to the validity and alignment of indicators used by the researchers just to their established research objectives. Commonly, as many researchers employ quantitative research design specifically descriptive research, researchers find convenience in the development and construction of researcher-made survey-questionnaire. Questionnaires are often as part of research studies to collect data from participants. Hence, the information obtained through a questionnaire is dependent on how it has been designed, used and validated. In this line, a research questionnaire as data collection tool is consisting of series of questions or items that are used to collect information from respondents and learn about their knowledge, opinions, attitudes, beliefs and behaviors.

Consequently, survey-questionnaire is a technique for gathering statistical information about to some or all members of the population. Thus, the ubiquity of the surveys provide broad coverage of the chosen population in a research work (Earth and Planetary Sciences, 2025). Survey questionnaire under the survey research is a useful and legitimate approach to research that has clear benefits in helping describe and explore the variables (Ponto, 2015). The survey-questionnaire as an instrument commonly used in quantitative researches should obtain validity and reliability. The face and content validity of the instrument are common considerations in the development of a researcher-made survey-questionnaire (Cabanilla Jr., 2023). Common considerations in the development and use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire is its criterion validity and that test-retest validity should be addressed given in wide-spread implementation of the tool (Kersten et al., 2015). It is important to consider the postulates and complexities of the questionnaire fundamentals, technical challenges and sequential flow of steps to build a reliable and valid questionnaire (Kishore et al., 2021). The researchers find a strong research gap specifically knowledge gap because of the examined previous published researchers are only concentrated in examining the main considerations in the development of questionnaire in a research work. In this line, the researchers assessed the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire. Aside from the research this examined research gap, the researchers observed actual conditions in their respective fields that most of their colleagues and learners put less emphasis on the significant considerations in the development and use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire when administering quantitative studies. In addition, the researchers observed that most their learners and colleagues are only reliant to the development of questions or items without emphasizing the relevance, alignment and consistency of the developed items or questions in the developed survey-questionnaire.

In view of the foregoing conditions observed by the researchers, they assessed the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire in conducting quantitative studies. Hence, significance of this study is vested on the provision of scientific analysis as to the assessed extend on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire of randomly selected public school teachers in the Philippines.

OBJECTIVES

This study assessed the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire among public school teachers in the Philippines. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. How may teachers' assess the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire in terms of customization and relevance aspects?
2. How do teachers benefit in the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire in the conduct of quantitative studies in terms of flexibility, contained tailored indicators, cost-effective and highly-engaging?
3. What are the challenges encountered in using researcher-made survey-questionnaire by teachers in terms of validity, reliability testing, time-consumption and potential bias?
4. Based from the findings, what program intervention may be proposed to help teachers develop or expand their technical knowledge in the development and utilization of researcher-made survey-questionnaire in education-related studies?

METHODOLOGY

The study used a quantitative method which specifically employed descriptive research design. Apparently, the researchers used simple random sampling where they selected the participation of 300 public school teachers who are comprised by 150 elementary and 150 secondary teachers. The researchers used a developed survey-questionnaire as the instrument of the study. It contained three (3) parts in which part 1 contained items relating

to teachers' extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire. On one hand, part 2 contained items relating to the benefits obtained by teachers in using researcher-made survey-questionnaire while part 3 contained items relating to the challenges encountered by teachers in using a researcher-made survey-questionnaire. Thus, items under part 1 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of $\alpha=.817$ which meant that the items were acceptable while items under part 2 gained a Cronbach Alpha result of $\alpha=.713$ which meant that the items were also acceptable. Lastly, items under part 3 obtained a Cronbach Alpha result of $\alpha=.819$ which meant that the items were acceptable. The developed survey-questionnaire used a 4-Likert Scale with different verbal descriptions under each part. For part 1, it used a scale of: 4-High Extent, 3-Moderate Extent, 2-Low Extent and 1-Very Low Extent while for part 2 it used a scale of: 4-Strongly Agree, 3-Agree, 2-Disagree and 1-Strongly Disagree. Then, for part 3 it used a scale of: 4-Always Encountered, 3-Often Encountered, 2-Seldom Encountered and 1-Not Encountered. On the other hand, the researchers used a Google Form to facilitate their actual data collection. When all the data have been organized, the researchers applied relevant statistical tools such as the use of frequency, mean and general weighted mean. Thus, the researchers distributed formal invitation letters to the respondents, informed consent and assent forms which also reflected their compliance to the ethical standards in the conduct of an independent research study. Hence, data were stored on researchers' personal devices and were destroyed after the completion of this research work. No access links were provided for the respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Researcher-made survey-questionnaire is essential research instrument under the scientific data collection paradigm. This enable the researchers to gather quantitative data or information drawn and expressed by a certain research work's selected respondents. Apparently, the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire has not been emphasized if not, fail to provide certain scientific importance. This study filled this gap as it assessed the extent on the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire to facilitate the data collection structure in quantitative studies along with education-related researches.

1. **Extent on the Use of Researcher-Made Survey-Questionnaire.** The result showed that customization obtained the highest mean of 3.68, described as high extent while relevance aspect gained a mean of 3.56, also described as high extent. This implied that the respondents emphasized effective ways in tailoring their developed items or questions to fit in the context, nature and scope of their research works. In this line, the results further revealed that the respondents formulated items and questions which directly addressed their established research objectives or answered directly their formulated research questions aligned with the nature and contextual limitations of their research work. Also, the result implied that with proper customization, the respondents highly extended the shape and forms of their developed items or questions the potentially gather relevant information or data from their respondents. On one hand, on relevance aspect, the respondents assessed the this aspect is considered with high extent as the result indicated that the developed items or questions were consistent to the topics being studies. In other words, the results showed that emphasis on relevance adhered to the strong alignment with the established research goals. In addition, the results also implied that the developed questions and items contained in their formulated survey-questionnaire potentially lead to accuracy and attract comprehensive responses from their targeted respondents. Results of the study supported the study of Honan et al.(2013) which revealed that adequacy and relevance of the developed survey-questionnaire were imperative to gather accurate data.
2. **Benefits from the Use of Researcher-Made Survey-Questionnaire.** The results showed that highly engaging aspect gained a highest mean of 3.79, described as strongly agree while contained tailored indicators obtained the second highest mean of 3.72, also described as strongly agree. Meanwhile, the results also revealed that cost-effective and flexibility gained mean scores of 3.56 and 3.52 respectively, both described as strongly agree. Teachers strongly agreed that when they use a researcher-made survey-questionnaire it captured their respondents' interests and encouraged them to actively engaged in the data collection processes when they administered education-related studies which used quantitative method. The results also showed that when the teachers gained high level of engagement through the researcher-made survey-questionnaire, they could be able to

increase the response rates from their respondents and that the quality of responses were more likely to invest time and thoughts to answer such instrument. On one hand, teachers strongly agreed that they gained benefits from using a researcher-made survey-questionnaire as the same emphasized the practical reflection of their respondents' thoughts and ideas. In this line, the results further emphasized that specificity of indicators and adaptability were obtained as teachers strongly agreed that when researcher-made survey-questionnaire was used, they could be able to align directly such indicators to their research objectives and established more specific items or questions. Further, the results also showed that teachers strongly agreed that the researcher-made survey-questionnaire enabled them spend less because they could no longer purchase nor acquire standardized questionnaire which practically, expensive. In addition, teachers strongly agreed that they could be able to adapt items or questions in their own format and style of presenting the indicators. In this way, teachers further strongly agreed that their respondents' responses were more contextual. Results of the study supported the study of Laaksonen (2018) which concluded that adequate questionnaire construction was critical to the success. Similar study also revealed that correct ordering of questions, correct scaling caused the increased on responses rate.

3. **Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Using a Researcher-Made Survey-Questionnaire.** The result showed that teachers always encountered difficulty in the reliability testing and validation of the researcher-made survey-questionnaire which both obtained the highest mean of 3.68, described as always encountered. Also, teachers do not encountered that researcher-made survey-questionnaire was time consuming and with potential bias which obtained mean scores of 1.72 and 1.68 respectively, described as not encountered. The results showed that teachers are challenged and experienced frequent struggle with the conduct of reliability testing and validation process of their constructed survey-questionnaire. This indicated that they found it challenging to conduct reliability test which caused additional work in the conduct of their researches. Additionally, they were also challenged as testing procedures offered complex processes. On one hand, teachers were not challenged as they found that the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire was time-efficient and posed limited bias. Further, the results showed that teachers felt confident that when they used this instrument, they potentially minimize or eradicate bias, placing items to neutral and adhered to fairness. Results of the study supported the study of Borreo (2023) which asserted that teachers assessed themselves slightly competent in conducting reliability test and validation process when they administer action researches.
4. **Proposed Program Intervention.** Based from the results of the study, following were key areas to consider in the development of impactful program intervention which may help teachers develop their technical know-how in developing and using a researcher-made survey-questionnaire: (1) administer hands-on technical workshop in the computation of reliability test using Cronbach Alpha, (2) formulate school-based survey-questionnaire toolkits, (3) administer a mentorship and support networks building support groups who would technically assist teachers from the development to testing until the actual use of their researcher-made survey-questionnaire.

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CONCLUSION

Researcher-made survey-questionnaire is commonly used as research instruments in the administration of quantitative researches. This research instrument is widely used across various fields including education and social sciences. The study revealed that teachers assessed researcher-made survey-questionnaire as highly practical and easy to utilize because of its customization and relevance aspects. In addition, the study further concluded that teachers experienced several benefits in the use of researcher-made survey-questionnaire as it is

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